

Improving Position Tracking for Pedestrian Focused Location Based Services in Challenging Urban Environments

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Summary

Location Based Services (LBS) require an ability to automatically track the user's position. There are a variety of technologies able to do this, including wi-fi positioning, cell tower triangulation, various Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS) constellations, as well as inertial measurement units (IMUs). This paper focuses on techniques and methods that improve the accuracy of outdoor pedestrian positioning in urban contexts – a place where locational accuracy can vary considerably, depending on the canyoning effect of buildings and the time of day (the LOS of positioning satellites causing a dilution of precision). In particular we look at real-time map matching and how elevation data can provide useful additional inputs to position determination.

KEYWORDS: Map matching, LBS, urban space, pedestrian tracking, GNSS.

1. Introduction

The value of accurate pedestrian tracking in indoor and outdoor environments is well understood with an increasing interest in providing services to pedestrians that depend on precise knowledge of their whereabouts (Retscher, 2004). Global satellite based positioning technologies, such as GPS, are able to calculate a three dimensional location wherever the satellite's signals can be detected, however multipath signals arise where the pedestrian's device does not have direct lines of sight to the satellites – made worse for pedestrians (compared with cars) since they are positioned on the pavement, and close to tall buildings (Figure 1). Additionally pedestrian movements are not confined by road usage laws (swap sides of the road, stop and turn on the spot, backtrack, use steps, and criss-cross open spaces (plazas, parks). Furthermore the device may be concealed in a bag or pocket resulting in signal deterioration or loss. Satellite based positioning technologies do not provide the means to calculate a user's heading other than by monitoring position changes over time which is why additional services and sensors are required to improve the tracking of the pedestrian. Even with high sensitivity GPS chipsets able to resolve locations in urban canyons and take advantage of the growing number of different constellations (Lachapelle, 2004) positional errors still occur. This paper demonstrates how real-time map matching can be used to improve the positional robustness of urban pedestrians.

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Figure 1: View of Sky (angle in degrees) based on Proximity to Buildings.
 For a typical city pedestrian up to a third of the sky can be occluded by buildings.

2. Local Positioning Technologies

There are a range of technologies that can be used to improve positional accuracy, each with various strengths, processing costs and latency. Given the dynamic nature of pedestrian tracking some methodologies are not suitable, for example scene-analysis (Kray and Kortuem, 2004; Randerson, 2004) and SLAM (Botterill, 2010) due to high processing requirements, and requiring the user to wear an additional sensors. An alternate approach which avoids equipping users with additional hardware is to provide a supporting real-time map matching service.

2.1. Global Navigation Satellite System

In the interests of pragmatism and wider application, we utilised GNSS as the positioning technology. Figure 2 shows the simultaneous data tracks recorded on a GPS-only and GPS+GLONASS device. The radius of the line denotes the error (in metres) reported. The GLONASS+GPS solution (green) exhibits a more stable path than GPS-only though it exhibits an offset to the south along the entire journey. For certain applications this level of accuracy will suffice, but for more advanced LBS, such as virtual city agents which model visibility space, knowing which side of the street a pedestrian is on makes a huge difference to the field of view.

Figure 2: Error reporting - GPS versus GPS + GLONASS logged tracks

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2.2. Pedestrian Accessibility Model

The idea of snapping to the road centre line (Quddus, Ochieng and Noland, 2007), as used in vehicle positioning (Basnayake and Lachapell, 2003; Syed, 2004), was not appropriate for pedestrians who enjoy much greater degrees of freedom. Many map matching algorithms work by post-processing trajectory data, and can therefore consider both the previous and next points of a trajectory (e.g. Millard-Ball, Hampshire and Weinberger, 2019).

For real-time map matching we created a Pedestrian Accessibility Model (PAM) based on a raster surface at 1m resolution that represents the likelihood that a pedestrian could occupy that space based on the land use. It is assumed that pavements are more attractive than roads, and roads much more attractive than buildings. Open spaces are considered slightly less attractive than pavements, tracks and pathways, but more attractive than road regions. Water bodies and cliff regions are considered very unlikely. Interpolated values between these regions were used to derive the direction in which to ‘push’ the reported user position towards the most likely region. For example if the reported location is on a building, the aspect of the slope indicates the most likely direction required for the correction. In Figure 3 the ‘elevation’ value represents the probability of user occupancy (higher values = less likely). Therefore all buildings appear like equal heighted ‘loaves’, and pavements appear as gutters - the user’s location could be considered as a marble rolling through this ‘loaf like’ world.

Figure 3: Pedestrian Accessibility Model (PAM)
– perspective map view of the most accessible regions and likely areas to find pedestrians

2.3. Use of Elevation Information

The user’s position history and a Digital Terrain Model (DTM) were also used in modelling the candidate space surrounding the pedestrian. Figure 4 shows an example of where this monitoring can be used to eliminate the possibility that the user moved to the road under the bridge [marker 1], by allocating a low probability to the regions with large elevation changes compared to the user’s previous location. This ensures the processed position is not permitted to fall on to this lower road [marker 2].

Google Streetview from [2] looking towards [1]

Figure 4: Digital Terrain Model used in Bridge Track Corrections User walks across a bridge[1] passing over lower road [2]

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Google StreetView © 2021

2.4. Map matching position correction

The position correction process was implemented as a cloud service over a cell network, and involved taking the reported position from the smartphone, searching the immediate surrounding area and selecting the most likely location of the user ('the corrected position') based on where they were just prior, and the type of entity they are most likely to be walking (defined by the PAM). The following methodology was applied at each position update (1Hz):

- Create a 60m x 60m Candidate Space of 1m x 1m cells around the GNSS reported location
- Calculate pace rate from the phone's accelerometer data (acting as a pedometer)
- Calculate the average speed over the last 1s, 2s and 3 seconds from GNSS data
- Calculate the average orientation over the last 1s, 2s and 3s from GNSS data
- Check the PAM to determine the most likely locations (ie not roofs, more likely pavement)
- Weight locations in front of the user as more likely next locations (based on GNSS orientation)
- Use average speed values to determine the maximum likely distance the user could have moved since last GNSS update. Create Euclidean decay mask based from a point projected forward this distance from current best guess of location
- Compare the previous ground elevation value with those in candidate space, and decrease the probability for cells which have a difference of more than 3m in a travel time of 1 second.
- Assign a confidence level to the corrected location based on comparisons (e.g. pace rate vs GNSS speed, GNSS reported location vs modelled location, land use type)

The function is used recursively with increasing tolerances, until a suitable location is found. In addition the most likely road centreline location is determined through vector point to line snapping, and used to seed the search when a local minima has occurred from searches beginning from the original GNSS location. The output is a candidate space filled with values which represent the likelihood that the user is occupying that position (Figure 5).

Figure 5: Location Probabilities in the Candidate Space around the Reported GNSS Location

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3. Results

Figure 6: Correcting the reported location using map matching

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Figure 6 and Figure 7 show the likely path (green triangles) based on the GNSS data (orange dots) using this methodology. Both show the user's location has been corrected to the pavement areas. Notice in Figure 7(a) at marker 1 that the GNSS error is large enough to force the processed location to the wrong side of the road. Figure 7 (b) for a different journey, includes additional snapped road centreline points (marker 3). For navigation tasks this road centreline is sufficient, but for visibility modelling it's

important to model views from the correct side of the road and observer's elevation (i.e. not roof tops). Marker 2 shows where the processed location has jumped across a building as a result of determining the GNSS track to be closest to the more northern road. This is corrected a few seconds later when the Pedestrian Tracker re-selects the main road as the main candidate based on its distance and orientation. For any large jumps such as these, the Pedestrian Tracking service reports a low level of confidence in the corrected location, given the unstable nature of the trajectory. Any LBS using the location can then wait until a more robust position update is available.

Figure 7: User moving along pavement, with original and processed position tracks displayed (a) and the road centreline snap point (b)

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4. Discussion and Future work

Our focus here is how we can use geographical constraints and likely paths to reduce uncertainty arising from the inaccuracy of tracking technologies. The use of a PAM helps to limit erroneous results, and reduce the number of incorrect locations logged. Furthermore the pedestrian tracker is able to use additional smartphone sensor data in the processed location output, and assign a confidence to that location.

Here we have not implemented a GNSS shadow matching solution (Groves, 2011), but would be worth considering for the future. This improves the side of street positioning through considering 3D building data with reported GNSS signal strengths to estimate where the direct lines-of-sight to satellites are blocked.

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6. Biographies

Dr Phil Bartie is an assistant professor in computer science at Heriot-Watt University, where he carries out research in spatial data science. This ranges from analysing big data to gain a better understanding of space and place, to building contextually aware systems and user interfaces.

Dr William Mackaness is a senior lecturer in Geosciences at University of Edinburgh. His research is concerned with the application of statistical and visualisation techniques to geographical problem solving. He also is interested in theories of scale, the characterisation of geographic space, location based services and wayfinding.